

Structured Interview Script with AI:

- **Initial Context:** “Extreme weather events have become increasingly frequent and severe in Brazil and around the world. Their impacts are wide-ranging, affecting various production chains and directly impacting essential services such as electricity distribution. This service, due to its public nature and capillarity, is particularly sensitive to the occurrence of extreme events and, at the same time, critical for response and recovery in emergency situations. In this context, discussions around mitigation and adaptation measures to climate change have become increasingly relevant, aiming to ensure the continuity, quality, and efficiency of electricity services. However, these measures involve complex decisions, with costs and benefits that affect different actors in different ways. Therefore, this study seeks to explore different perspectives — including distributors, transmission companies, the ONS, ANEEL, MME, Civil Defense, consumers, investors, other utilities, suppliers, insurers, academia, meteorologists, NGOs, the media, and civil society — to understand how each perceives the challenges related to extreme weather events in the electricity sector.”
- **Question 1:** “In this situation, what is the problem that each party believes they are facing? How do these views overlap or diverge?”
- **Question 2:** “If this problematic situation persists, who will be most affected and how?”
- **Question 3:** “To what extent are current practices aligned with the outcomes we want? What is effectively preventing us from changing?”
- **Question 4:** “What tensions are currently present among the various stakeholders? How can we use them as a source of innovation?”
- **Question 5:** “Considering the different perspectives, what would be a solution that honors the best of each one?”
- **Question 6:** “Are the proposed solutions viable, both from an economic standpoint and in terms of implementation time? Do they favor certain groups over others, or do they genuinely manage to reconcile the various interests involved?”
- **Question 7:** “It should be noted that the effectiveness of the proposed solution requires the active participation of different actors from the design phase through to implementation. Brazil, being a country of continental dimensions, is highly heterogeneous: some cities and states are heavily affected by extreme events, while others experience them in a much milder or almost nonexistent way. Given the effort and costs involved in implementing this solution, how can we encourage the

engagement of all stakeholders, including those less affected? How can we effectively communicate the increase in costs while managing the paradox between diversification and integration?”

- **Question 8:** “In the Brazilian electricity sector, it is often said that ‘Brazil is the country of cheap energy and expensive electricity bills.’ This contradiction is partly explained by the presence of numerous charges and subsidies in the electricity tariff, which go beyond the actual cost of energy and service provision. Many of these subsidies benefit specific classes of consumers or segments of the production chain, resulting in the privatization of gains and the socialization of costs. At the same time, the main sectoral charge — the Energy Development Account (CDE) — has not received a significant contribution from the Federal Government in years. Given this scenario, a critical question arises: how can the tariff be used as a funding source for the solution if there is no longer any ‘tariff slack’ to accommodate new costs?”
- **Question 9:** “The exercise of evaluating different perspectives shows that investors, distributors, and the regulator converge in valuing regulatory predictability. However, addressing the problematic situation under discussion requires change and innovation — which tend to be supported by the first two when there is a potential gain, but often face regulatory bureaucracy inclined to preserve the status quo in light of the ‘preservation versus evolution’ paradox. How can this paradox be managed? How important is academia in this context?”
- **Question 10:** “In the end, it is complex to create regulatory incentive mechanisms that work effectively for all distributors. Few regulators in the world face a scenario as challenging as Brazil’s, marked by strong heterogeneity and a large number of concessionaires. Treating each distributor individually may promote greater equity but imposes a high regulatory cost, compromising the efficiency of the model. Taking the case of Light in Rio de Janeiro as an example, it becomes clear that the difficulty in restoring service after adverse environmental events stems not only from the impact of the event itself, but also from the distributor’s limited access to certain areas of the concession. Many of these areas experience high rates of theft and default, are dominated by militias or drug gangs, and in some cases, the distributor is unable to enter at all. How can innovative regulation deal with such outliers while maintaining operational viability without compromising principles of efficiency and equity?”